

Analysis of surface roughness and vibrations during micro ball end milling with various ramping directions

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Abstract. This study focuses on dependencies between the tool effective diameter and dynamics, as well as the machined surface quality obtained in the micro ball end milling of hardened steel with various ramping directions. As part of this research analytical expressions of tool effective diameter in case of micro ball end milling of inclined surfaces have been formulated. Moreover, the micro-milling tests involving the measurements of accelerations of vibrations and machined surface roughness parameters were carried out. These tests included the micro ball end milling with surface inclinations of 15° in upward and downward ramping strategies. It has been found that distribution of tool effective diameter and cutting speed values in micro ball end milling with ramping strategies depend on tool nominal diameter, surface inclination and depth of cut in axial direction. The direction of ramping strategy significantly influences the surface roughness parameters values, as well as the amplitudes and power spectral density (PSD) charts of vibrations generated during micromachining process. The larger values of a measured process outputs were found during the downward ramping, which can be attributed to the lower values of cutting speeds distributed along the active cutting edge.

Keywords: Micro-milling, Surface Roughness, Vibrations, Ball End Mill.

1 Introduction

The fundamental aspect of the precision machining (PM) and ultra-precision machining processes (UPM) is significant improvement in machined surface finish [1 – 3].

According to Dornfeld and Lee [4], the classification of cutting into ultra-precise, precise and conventional can be done concerning the uncut chip thickness values, as well as the chip decohesion process phenomena. During conventional machining, the chip formation results directly from material decohesion appearing in a shear zones.

However, during a precise and ultra-precise cutting, the phenomenon of chip formation is attributed also to non-zeroth cutting edge radius, which affects the intense ploughing/burnishing of a workpiece [5, 6], and certain factors characterizing the workpiece that are overlooked in conventional machining. Among mentioned factors the: micro-pores and material cracks, inclusions, boundaries of grains, interactions of dislocation, as well as the structure of the workpiece can be distinguished [7]. The PM and UPM techniques are focused on manufacturing of parts with a restrictive constraints regarding the surface and dimensional quality. Moreover, these cutting processes are very often carried out with use of micro end mills, with a diameter values below 1 millimeter. The extreme requirements towards a surface quality and process stability constitute the fundamental problems of the precise and micro-milling processes [8-11]. Thus, the identification of specific physical phenomena in machined surface topography generation and selection of process conditions allowing improvement of surface finish with milling economics and dynamic stability are constituting the up-to-date challenge.

During micromilling processes, an area of cut significantly differs from that appearing during the macro-milling. These differences result from the significant effect of machining system geometrical errors (e.g. tool run out), tool deflections caused by forces, as well as the burnishing/elastic deformations of workpiece affecting the tool entry/exit angles and instantaneous uncut chip thickness values. Therefore, Zhang et al. [12] proposed the model of uncut chip thickness for the micromilling including the derivation of a variable input and output angles induced by tool deflection and run out. In their approach the instant uncut chip thickness has been evaluated concerning the minimum uncut chip thickness, modelled instantaneous uncut chip thickness and a parameter characterizing material decohesion mechanisms. Sahoo et al. [13] proposed an improved uncut chip thickness method concerning the variable run out of tool, trochoidal trajectory of cutting edge, minimum chip thickness, as well as the elastic recovery. In addition, the research carried out by Yuan et al. [14] demonstrated that in micromilling, the current value of uncut chip thickness can be affected by values of material elastic recovery remaining from previous tool rotations. This accumulation phenomenon can consequently have an influential impact on the micro-milling dynamics. It should be noted that problem of uncut chip thickness accumulation was investigated by Wojciechowski et al. [15]. They demonstrated that instant oscillations of cutting forces observed in micromilling in a ploughing regime are caused by a machining regime transitions, resulting from so-called chip thickness accumulation. It is also responsible for nonlinearities of averaged forces in a range of a minimum uncut chip thickness value. The above discussed problems are characteristic for the micro-milling processes with the end mills. However, the micro ball-end-milling process of a curvilinear surfaces can be also significantly affected by the machined surface inclinations, milling strategies, and complex geometry of a cutter [16-18]. Shan et al. [19], indicated that displacements of thin-walled machined material (stainless steel), as well as cutting forces during micro ball-end-milling are strongly influenced by a surface inclination angle. Similar observations were made by Wojciechowski [20] in the study involving the modeling and measurement of cutting forces in ball end milling of hardened steel.

It was observed that the most intense influence on forces was observed in the range of surface inclination angles: $0 \leq \alpha \leq 15^\circ$. Apart from forces and deformations, the surface inclination angles, as well as a strategy of milling process affect the formation of a machined surface topography, process dynamics and stability, as well as the tool life. The study conducted by Yuan et al. [21] shows that during micro ball-end-milling of a complex surfaces (made of stainless steel), the values of milling errors are influentially attributed to machining strategy, connected with surface inclinations. Ozturk et al. [22] indicated that cutting geometry, mechanics and dynamics vary drastically and non-linearly with a changes in lead and tilt angles. Gök et al. [23], have observed that in ball end milling of curvilinear surfaces, tool-acceleration values obtained for the convex inclined surfaces were found to be smaller in comparison to ones reached during milling of the concave inclined surfaces. According to Authors, this dependency was attributed to the easier chip removal from the cutting zone during machining of a convex surface. Buj-Corral et al. [24] indicated, that reduction of the surface roughness of a hot work tool steel can be made by ball end milling in ascendant trajectories with down milling kinematics. However during the ball end milling in descendant trajectories, the up milling is recommended. Vopát et al. [25] investigated the tool wear during ball end milling of C45 steel in downward and upward ramping strategies. They obtained that tool wear on the flank face during downward ramping was smaller than that obtained after upward ramping. According to Authors, this dependency can be explained by a higher area of contact between tool and workpiece during downward ramping.

The above deliberations reveal that the type and direction of a ball end milling strategy plays an important role regarding the physical phenomena and process technological effects. It is mainly attributed to the variations in force distribution along the cutting edge, as well as the changes in tool entry and exit angles, as a function of surface inclinations. The another important factor is a tool effective diameter, which in turn influences the values of cutting speeds. It should be noted that the impact of tool effective diameter on cutting speed values is particularly important during micro-milling, where the employed tool diameters and depths of cut are relatively small, thus contributing to small values of cutting speeds. Nevertheless, relations between the surface inclination values, as well as the direction of a milling strategy (affecting the effective diameter), and the obtained milling effects, have not been yet investigated sufficiently. Moreover, there is still research gap concerning the effect of ramping direction on the ball end milling effects. Therefore, in this study the analysis regarding the relations between the ramping direction and micro ball end milling process effects is made. The primary novelty of this work is the identification of a link between the tool effective diameter (and thus cutting speed) values and process effects, as measured accelerations of vibrations of a machining system and surface roughness. Hence, this study proposes an analytical model for a ball end mill effective diameter, depended on machining parameters and ramping milling direction. The structure of paper contains the state-of-the-art, then analytical characteristics of effective diameter during ramping milling. After that, an experiment involving the micro milling tests and analysis of surface roughness and milling vibrations was made.

2 Effective Diameter of a Ball End Mill during Milling with a Ramping Strategy

Tool diameter variations in the interface between the workpiece and cutting edge are affected by the ball end mill working part's spherical geometry. Thus, during ball end milling, the effective diameter D_{ef} has to be distinguished, which is correlated with point on the cutting edge, which stays in contact with workpiece (see – Figs. 1-3). On the basis of trigonometric dependencies, it is seen that D_{ef} parameter value depends on nominal diameter D of tool, depth of cut in axial direction a_p and surface inclination angle α . Moreover, the effective diameter D_{ef} value in ball end milling changes along the cutting edge active length. It should be noted, that effective diameter influences a cutting speed value. Therefore, in ball end milling process, a cutting speed is described by equation:

$$v_c = \pi \cdot D_{ef} \cdot n \quad (1)$$

where: v_c is cutting speed, D_{ef} is effective diameter, n is rotational speed.

The ball end milling is usually carried out with the application of ramping strategies. Therefore, the determination of an effective diameter for these cutting modes is of high importance. In case of upward ramping, the tool effective diameter values are contained within the range between the D_{ef1} and D_{ef2} (Fig. 1).

The values of D_{ef1} and D_{ef2} can be described by equations:

$$D_{ef1} = D \cdot \sin \alpha \quad (2)$$

$$D_{ef2} = D \cdot \sin \left(\alpha + \arccos \left(\frac{R - a_p}{R} \right) \right) \quad (3)$$

where: D_{ef1} is tool effective diameter at the point 1 onto the active length of cutting edge, D_{ef2} is tool effective diameter at the point 2 onto the active length of cutting edge, D is tool nominal diameter, R is nominal radius, a_p depth of cut in axial direction, α is surface inclination angle.

During this machining mode, the lowest effective diameter D_{ef1} is always higher than 0, thus the cutting speed values are never $v_c = 0$ m/min. During the downward ramping, the two distinct geometric modes, diversified in terms of a selected depth of cut and surface inclination angle can be found (Figs. 2, 3). In case when the selected depth of cut is not reaching the point 0 onto the cutting edge, the effective diameter is contained within the range between the D_{ef1} and D_{ef3} . The value of D_{ef3} can be described by the equation:

$$D_{ef3} = D \cdot \sin \left(\alpha - \arccos \left(\frac{R - a_p}{R} \right) \right), \text{ when: } a_p < R \cdot (1 - \cos \alpha) \quad (4)$$

where: D_{ef3} is tool effective diameter at the point 3 onto the active length of cutting edge.

Fig. 1. Effective diameter during the upward ramping.

During this cutting mode – similarly to upward ramping process – the effective diameter D_{ef1} is higher than 0, however the cutting speeds can take the very low values, when the selected depths of cut are contained in a vicinity of the point 0. During the downward ramping with the depth of cut which reaches or exceeds the point 0, the effective diameter values are contained within the range between the D_{ef1} and D_{ef4} . In this cutting mode, the value of D_{ef4} can be described by the equation:

$$D_{ef4} = D \cdot \sin \left(\arccos \left(\frac{R - a_p}{R} \right) - \alpha \right), \text{ when: } a_p \geq R \cdot (1 - \cos \alpha) \quad (5)$$

where: D_{ef4} is tool effective diameter at the point 4 onto the active length of cutting edge.

Fig. 2. Effective diameter during the downward ramping with depth of cut below the point 0.

Nevertheless, the directions of cutting speeds in points 1 and 4 located onto the cutting edge always have opposite directions. Moreover, the effective diameter in point 0 is equal to 0 and thus the cutting speed in this point is 0 as well. This observation indicates that during downward ramping, the back cutting phenomenon can occur, together with an intense ploughing/elastic deformation of workpiece near the point 0. These phenomena can have the significant influence on a cutting thermo-mechanics occurring during the chip formation, and thus on the formation of a machined surface texture.

Fig. 3. Effective diameter during the downward ramping with depth of cut equal or above the point 0.

3 Materials and methods

The experiments involved the micro-milling of hardened tool alloy 1.2713 steel, with a medium hardness of 55 HRC. The carbide micro ball end mills with TiAlN coating were applied in milling tests. The micro tools had geometry: nominal diameter $D = 1$ mm, number of teeth $z = 2$, orthogonal rake angle $\gamma_o = -10^\circ$, orthogonal flank angle $\alpha_o = 6^\circ$, helix angle $\lambda_s = 30^\circ$. Micromilling experiments were made on a precise Haas UMC-750 machine tool. Milling experiments were carried out using the upward and downward ramping strategies with use of accelerometer (Figs. 4a-c).

Fig. 4. The scheme of: a) upward ramping; b) downward ramping.

The milling parameters used in tests are presented in Table 1. In this table, the calculated values of cutting speed, based on equations (1)-(5) were also included. In a carried out tests the pick feed value fulfilled the condition: $b_r < D_{ef1} \wedge D_{ef2}$. Therefore, the subsequent tool passes were overlapping.

The micromilling tests included also the evaluation of accelerations of vibrations in micro-milling and measurement of a machined surface roughness. Vibrations were evaluated with the application of 1-axis piezoelectric PCB 352B10 accelerometer clamped to the workpiece. This sensor has been applied to the measurement of accelerations of vibrations in the feed direction.

Surface roughness was inspected with use of TOPO – 01P stylus surface profiler. In conducted measurements the length of cut-off wave 0.8 mm, sampling length of 0.2 mm, the evaluation length of 2.5 mm, and Gauss filter were applied. The measurements have been conducted three times for the each of investigated combinations of machining conditions in order to evaluate the average measured values. On the basis of generated 2D surface profiles, the Ra and Rz parameters' values were calculated with use of dedicated software.

Table 1. Micro ball end milling conditions during ramping strategy.

α [°]	f_z [μm]	n [rev/min]	a_p [μm]	b_r [μm]	v_{c1} upward [m/min]	v_{c1} downward [m/min]	v_{c2} [m/min]	v_{c4} [m/min]
15	25	5000	50	25	4.1	4.2	10.3	3
15	25	10 000	50	25	8.1	8.4	20.5	5.9

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Analysis of Vibrations

Figure 5 shows the acquired root mean square (RMS) values of accelerations of vibrations A_f during micro-milling in upward and downward ramping. It was observed that independently on a selected tool rotational speed n , the significantly lower vibrations A_f appeared during the upward ramping milling. In case of micro-milling with

$n = 5000$ rev/min, the differences between the RMS values of vibrations in both investigated cutting modes were 10-fold. During the micro-milling with $n = 10\ 000$ rev/min, these differences exceeded the 270%.

The reason of these large differences can be attributed to the distinct cutting speed distribution appearing in upward and downward ramping. In case of upward ramping, a cutting speed distribution along the length of cutting edge is contained within the range: $4.2\ \text{m/min} \leq v_c \leq 10.3\ \text{m/min}$ for $n = 5000$ rev/min and $8.4\ \text{m/min} \leq v_c \leq 20.5\ \text{m/min}$ for $n = 10\ 000$ rev/min. Therefore, the thermo-mechanically stable chip formation process appear (despite the relatively low cutting speeds), which have no implications with a process dynamics. Nevertheless, during downward ramping strategy, a cutting speed distribution along the length of cutting edge is contained within the range: $3\ \text{m/min} \leq v_c \leq 4.2\ \text{m/min}$ for $n = 5000$ rev/min and $5.9\ \text{m/min} \leq v_c \leq 8.4\ \text{m/min}$ for $n = 10\ 000$ rev/min. Therefore, the cutting speeds obtained during downward ramping are lower than those reached in upward ramping mode. In the carried out downward ramping experiment, the selected depth of cut was contained above the point 0 on the cutting edge (the case described in Fig. 3). Thus, the direction of cutting speeds in a lengths of cutting edge contained within the following points on the cutting edge: 0 to 1 and 0 to 4 was opposite. Consequently it led to the back cutting phenomenon during micro-milling. It should be also noted that cutting speeds contained in a vicinity of the 0 point on the cutting edge were close to zero.

Fig. 5. The root mean square values of accelerations of vibrations in feed direction during micro ball end milling with various ramping strategy directions.

The appearance of back cutting phenomenon together with very low values of cutting speed in a vicinity of the 0 point, can have the influential impact on chip formation mechanisms. These phenomena can be a source of irregular chip formation, intense ploughing and burnishing of a workpiece, as well as some dynamical interactions in a machining system, which consequently lead to the growth of vibrations during micro-milling in downward ramping strategy. Figure 5 shows also, that independently on micro-milling strategy, the higher vibrations are observed during process with $n = 10000$ rev/min. This relation can be related to forcing of some machining system's natural frequencies (e.g. the frequency of a workpiece) by a tooth passing frequency or its harmonics. In order to detect the vibration frequency constituents appearing during micro-milling, the power spectral density (PSD) charts of accelerations of vibrations were also developed (see Figs. 6a, b).

Fig. 6. The PSD spectra of accelerations of vibrations in feed direction during micro ball end milling with $n = 5000$ rev/min: a) upward strategy; b) downward strategy.

During the upward ramping (Fig. 6a), the accelerations of vibrations are dominated by the frequencies equal to 1200 Hz, 1800 Hz and 2100 Hz. The constituent of tooth passing frequency – reflecting the micro-milling kinematics (equal to 167 Hz) – can be also visible. However it has a relatively low amplitude. The appearance of peaks with frequencies of 1200 Hz, 1800 Hz and 2100 Hz is correlated directly with machining system's natural frequencies. In case of downward ramping (Fig. 6b), the above-mentioned frequencies are visible, however the vibration signal consists also of a many other constituents which are not correlated with process

kinematics or natural frequencies of a machining system. Therefore, these constituents can be related to appearance of back cutting and ploughing phenomena. However, it requires further studies.

4.2 Analysis of Surface Roughness

Surface roughness is one of fundamental factors characterizing the quality of manufactured parts and their maintenance [26]. Figures 7 and 8 depict the 2D surface profiles measured after the micro-milling in investigated cutting modes. During the upward ramping, the regular cutting edge projection into the workpiece – manifested by machining marks – is clearly visible. An appearance of machining marks is strictly correlated with feed and tool diameter/corner radius values [27]. The average distance between the asperities is equal to feed per revolution value $f = 50 \mu\text{m}$, instead of feed per tooth $f_z = 25 \mu\text{m}$. It indicates that in upward ramping, the surface topography generation is induced by the process kinematics and geometrical errors of machining system (run out). Nevertheless, no vibration marks are found on the machined surface profile, which confirms that process was dynamically stable. In case of downward ramping, the surface profile is significantly less regular and contains some random peaks with a relatively high amplitudes. This observation confirms that surface texture formation during downward ramping can be strongly affected by an irregular chip formation, intense ploughing and burnishing of a workpiece, as well as some dynamical interactions in a machining system resulting from downward ramping kinematics. The above observations can be also confirmed by the charts representing the surface roughness parameters: R_a and R_z (Figs. 9, 10). It can be noted that independently of a selected tool rotational speed n , the significantly lower surface roughness parameters' values were found during the upward ramping milling. In case of R_a parameter, these differences were up to 25%, but for the R_z parameter, they reached up to 215%.

Fig. 7. The machined surface 2D profile after micro ball end milling in upward ramping strategy with $n = 5000 \text{ rev/min}$.

Fig. 8. The machined surface 2D profile after micro ball end milling in downward ramping strategy with $n = 5000 \text{ rev/min}$.

Fig. 9. The comparison of surface roughness parameter Ra values during the micro ball end milling in upward and downward ramping strategies.

Fig. 10. The comparison of surface roughness parameter Rz values during the micro ball end milling in upward and downward ramping strategies.

Moreover, the higher values of surface roughness parameters were found during the micro-milling with a higher rotational speed. This observation is similar to that for the acceleration of vibration signals. Thus, the surface texture formation during micro ball end milling can be also strongly affected by machining system's vibrations with frequencies higher than tooth passing frequency.

5 Conclusions

Based on carried out analytical and experimental study, the following conclusions were formulated.

- During micro ball end milling in ramping strategies, the distribution of tool effective diameter and cutting speed values is dependent on: tool nominal diameter, surface inclination angle and axial depth of cut. Moreover, in case of downward ramping, the back cutting mechanism, manifested by the change in cutting speed vector as a function of tool rotation angle is found.
- Selection of ramping direction has quantitative and qualitative effect on a machined surface profile. In case of upward ramping, surface texture formation is affected by the process kinematics and geometrical errors of

machining system. However during downward ramping, surface profile is irregular and contains some random peaks with a relatively high amplitudes.

- Application of upward ramping in relation to downward ramping is advantageous in terms of vibrations and surface roughness minimization.

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